
Series: Physics and Astronomy

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Intelligent design and mathematics

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Annotation

An intelligent design for the creation of the Universe is realized under conditions when

- There is no something that the Universe is made of, otherwise the very concept of creation loses its meaning.
- There is no instrument by which the universe is made, otherwise the very concept of creation loses its meaning.
- There must be a design language that exists before creation
- There must be an author of the project

These conditions are met by the **Higher Mind**, existing outside the **Universe** (External Mind), and **mathematics** as a means (instrument), material and project for the creation of the Universe in the hands of the Higher Mind. Mathematics exists

objectively and that is why it can be used in this way. Man in the Universe is called upon to understand its construction and for this purpose he is created capable and willing to understand, and the Universe is made knowable. Thus, the Universe is aware of itself.

1. Intelligent design

The intelligent design theory, which has gained considerable popularity in recent years, was explicitly proposed by Darwin's critic, W. Paley, who proposed the famous concept of the "intelligent watchmaker" [1]. It began the search for such natural facts that could not be the result of random events, but should be recognized as the result of intelligent design. In 1996, a book [2] appeared, in which its author, Behe, *"examines the data of modern biochemical science, and claims that they are incompatible with both Darwin's evolutionary theory and its more modern modifications."* Here and below, I cite the article [3], which examines the ideas expressed in this book, as well as in reviews and articles that appeared after its publication. *"The book [2] is now considered a new word in the proof of the intelligent design of the creation of the Universe. Reviewing the data from modern biochemical science, Behe argues that they demonstrate "irreducibly complex," which can only be the result of intelligent design". In [3], he concludes: "if a system is truly irreducibly complex, it cannot be the product of intelligent design."*

Here's another example of how "irreducible complexity" serves as evidence against intelligent design. It is believed that the three-body problem - the task of calculating the trajectories of celestial bodies - has no definite solution, and the interaction of celestial bodies is chaotic. This, of course, contradicts the idea of intelligent design. "God does not play dice," said Einstein. I will add that God does not shuffle the stars. The equations of celestial mechanics, which do not have a deterministic and stable solution, do not describe the behavior of a real mechanical system. Thus, "irreducible complexity" becomes not an argument in favor of the idea of intelligent design, but an argument against this idea.

Thus, approximately 150 years of searching for a fact proving the existence of intelligent design have yielded no results. It seems impossible to find evidence of intelligent design without proposing some means of its implementation

The intelligent design theory was called upon to defend the concept of divine creation. And so "respectable" scientists who support the intelligent design theory do not say that this design has an author and avoid using the word God. But let's not be hypocritical - intelligent design has

an author, God, a Higher Mind, and an External Mind. We must admit that there is a Higher Mind outside the Universe, inaccessible to analysis and perception (as, for example, is infinity). Надо признать, что есть Высший Разум вне Вселенной, недоступный для анализа и восприятия (также, например, как бесконечность) and external, because it is beyond infinity. It must be admitted that we cannot analyze what is beyond infinity.

Religion needs intelligent design theory too. You can tell a child that the car is moving because dad is in it, and it will be true. But you need to explain it to an adult in more detail.

2. Organic life

I will refer first of all to the article by Gusev [4], where the following conclusion is made: "The structure of the genetic code, the structure of genomic sequences and the entire functional block of biochemical reactions, as a result of which the process of self-reproduction of living systems is realized, are determined not only by the physical and chemical properties of molecules, but also by the laws of abstract sciences – arithmetic, algebra and logic." Obviously, this means that in order to create living systems, it was first necessary to solve a mathematical problem. This is equivalent to the assertion that an External Mind participated in the origin of life. Thus, organic life was created after a certain complex mathematical problem was solved. It follows from this that before this creation there was an External Mind capable of solving this problem.

But how did organic matter become thinking? R. Descartes (1644) said, "God created the world and the laws of nature, and then the Universe acts as an independent mechanism." 200 years later, C. Darwin wrote, "There is grandeur in this view, according to which life with its various manifestations was originally breathed by the Creator into one or a limited number of forms; and while our planet continues to revolve according to the unchangeable laws of gravitation, from so simple a beginning an infinite number of the most beautiful and most wonderful forms have been and are being developed." However, many others say that the Mind that created our everything constantly interferes in worldly affairs, and does not (as a rule) let things take their course (self-organization). The creation of thinking matter will not be discussed here.

3. Inanimate matter

It does not follow from what has been said that the External Mind participated in the organization of inanimate matter. Next we will try to prove that the External Mind participated in this matter too.

In [2, 3, 4] it is shown that the equations of physics are a consequence of the principle of extreme total action (PETA). This principle is a generalization of the principle of least action, which is applicable only to those systems in which there are no heat losses. That is, the latter is practically not applicable anywhere, and in electrical engineering with its resistors this principle is not applicable in principle.

From the PEPD it follows that all equations of physics (Kirchhoff's equations, Maxwell's equations, equations of mechanics taking into account friction forces, equations of electrodynamics, equations of hydrodynamics, etc.) are conditions of the extremum of some functional. This functional ALWAYS has a SINGLE extremum, which creates an inviolable order in the universe. The natural appearance of such functionals without the intervention of External Mind is impossible.

4. Physical meaning and mass

If a physicist who is a "physicist to the core" does read my previous message, he will smirk and mutter: "Bullshit, which has absolutely no physical meaning!" If I am nearby, I will ask: "And what is physical meaning?" I have never heard an answer to this question, so I will try to give my own definition:

Physical meaning is a person's figurative representation of some real physical phenomenon. For example,

- a wave is a figurative representation of a sinusoidal function of spatial coordinate and time;
- energy is a quantity that can be calculated for any phenomenon or process;
- the law of conservation of energy is an empirically established regularity, which consists in the fact that if in some process the energy has decreased (increased) by a certain amount, then there is a process in which the energy has increased (decreased) by precisely the same amount.

The hardest thing, it seems to me, is to define mass, a particle. It is something that can be "taken to heart". What does mathematics have to do with it?

In [8, Chapter 4] it is shown (as a consequence of solving Maxwell's equations) that there can be a volume standing wave existing in the volume

of a strict cube. This volume has energy and mass. This volume neither emits nor absorbs energy. These properties are the properties of the wave existing in this volume. There are no "intra-cubic photons" that rush between the walls of the cube, and there are no walls - the wave itself limits the volume of the cube. A wave is a mathematical category. And all the listed properties of a cube are mathematical properties of a wave. It turns out that mass is a physical name for the mathematical property of this wave.

Note that the result is a cube that is AND a wave is AND a particle, and is hereinafter called WAP. This cube is an alternative to the quantum wave-particle, which can be either a particle or a wave (depending on unknown circumstances).

The reader might object that "a wave is the movement of photon particles; therefore, it is impossible to do without material particles as the fundamental principles of matter!" And he is right until it is proven that a wave can exist without photons. In [9], a proof is given for the statement that the photon is a physical illusion, and all the properties of the photon (due to which it appeared in science) can be explained by the fact that the electromagnetic wave rotates.

The existence of cubic particles seems implausible. However, waves can turn into particles not only in the microworld [12]. But then macroscopic ball lightning was discovered [24, 25, 26, 27], which passes through the glass like an electromagnetic wave, and a motionless and solid wave of water [23] appeared, against which ships crash. The photographs show square (or, in fact, cubic) sea waves. They are solid, and ships are wrecked when they collide with such waves. The existence of such waves proves that particles made of electromagnetic waves are mathematically justified. The electromagnetic wave in a particle is a set of 6 sinusoids: there are three sinusoids of electric strength and 3 sinusoids of magnetic strength. It is important to note that the three sinusoids are not three projections, but three independent sinusoids – independent in the sense that they change independently in dynamics. The system of Maxwell's equations unites all 6 sinusoids. This solution has no commonalities with the known wave solution, which is physically unacceptable, as it does not satisfy the law of conservation of energy [15].

For Maxwell's equations, a solution can be found that describes standing electromagnetic waves in the volume of a sphere [13]. Such a sphere can also be identified with a particle that exhibits both particle-like and wave-like properties. A spherical particle rotates. This phenomenon is observed in experiments and is described as spin, a certain quality of elementary particles that has no analogy in the macro world. The existence of a rotating particle-AND-wave destroys the boundary between the microworld and the macroworld: both worlds can be described by a single classical electrodynamics.

Inside the spherical particle, a standing electromagnetic wave pulsates along all its radii. The nodes of this wave are in the center and on the surface of the sphere. At the same time, a flow of electromagnetic energy pulsates along the radii, but this flow does not leave the sphere! The entire spherical electromagnetic wave rotates around a specific diameter of the sphere, which is perceived as the spin of the sphere (which has already been discussed).

A spherical wave has energy (like any wave). But the energy density on the surface of a sphere is zero. Energy density, as we know, is equal to pressure. Therefore, on the surface of a sphere, the internal pressure is zero!

Thus, we obtained a spherical particle,

- made from a wave,
- possessing energy and mass,
- rotating around its axis,
- having no pressure on its surface.

The size of this particle is not limited in any way, and it can be argued that some types of ball lightning are precisely such electromagnetic particles.

Now let's move from electrodynamics to gravitomagnetism. Due to the analogy between the mathematical descriptions of these sections of physics, we can assume that there are also spherical particles composed of gravitational waves. They should have the same properties. Apparently, the balls that the Earth creates [13] are such particles. They have no pressure on the surface of the sphere. However, the external pressure of the Earth exists and acts on this particle. Naturally, the total force of pressure is directed upwards, where there is less mass pressing on the particle ... and it rolls out!

But how does it form?! I don't know. But let's consider an analogy. A shapeless piece of easily deformable, but strong, light rubber fell into the depths of the waters. Under pressure from all sides, it will acquire a spherical shape and will be pushed to the surface. In the Earth's rock, an area can form whose chemical composition differs from that of the surrounding rock and is similar to that of the rubber in question. Let it also cool after formation. Then (in accordance with the above) it will take on a spherical shape, will be pushed to the surface, and petrify. In the photo from the specified site, it is clear that the ball is created in a "bottle", the substance of which is spent on creating the ball during some chemical reaction.

Therefore, it is proven that particles can exhibit both wave-like and particle-like properties simultaneously, rather than alternately. For more details, see [17]. A particle is a "wave-AND-particle" and not a "wave-OR-particle." In this case, probability becomes unnecessary for the mathematical description of the world. The idea that such a model should exist is not new. In 1900, the famous physicist and astronomer D. Jeans claimed that "in nature there are waves and only waves: closed waves, which we call matter, and unclosed waves, which we call radiation or light" [20]. E. Schrödinger held the same views until the end of his life, writing: "what we now take for particles are in fact waves" [21]. And the author of the concept of "wave-particle" dualism, de Broglie, also initially proceeded from the fact that "the waves described by quantum mechanics are the system itself" [22].

In a word, it is asserted that matter (including the human body) consists of waves, is made of waves as a set of sinusoids, i.e. **matter is made of sinusoids** (although this sounds childish). It can be said that materialism is wave materialism, in contrast to the materialism interpreted by the paradigm of materialism.

5. Energy

The second integral component of the Universe after mass is energy. It can be identified with mass. But still, when we talk about matter, we mean mass first of all. As we have seen, energy is present in conjunction with mass, but it can also exist independently. When we discuss energy, we often overlook the fact that it can be associated with mass. Energy exists in the form of an energy flow, in the form of an electromagnetic wave. This is a traveling wave, in which the energy flow is represented by the same six sinusoids, unified by Maxwell's system of equations. But the

solution of Maxwell's equations in this case differs significantly from the previous solution for a particle and, of course, from the known wave solution. Not all mathematical results have a physical interpretation. In general, there can be many solutions to Maxwell's equations as partial differential equations. More details about this can be found in [16]. Thus, **energy is made of sinusoids.**

6. How the brain sees matter

What does the brain see when it looks at the physical world? How do people see and hear what **exists** as electromagnetic waves?

In 1979, neurophysiologist Russell L. De Valois established that the brain does not respond to a picture consisting of pixels, but to spatial wave forms (which can be obtained by Fourier transforming such a picture into wave forms), i.e. brain cells did not respond to the original images, but to the wave forms of these images. Moreover, there are known experiments in which people (after a specific training) saw with their eyes closed. Thus, vision can be considered the perception of waveforms.

A hundred years before De Valois' discovery, the German physiologist and physicist Hermann von Helmholtz showed that the ear is also a frequency analyzer and perceives wave information. Later studies found that our olfactory organ is also based on so-called osmic frequencies [10].

Wave forms are electromagnetic waves. Therefore, an electrically conductive material must impede vision – be opaque, and a dielectric that does not impede the passage of electromagnetic waves must be transparent. This is observed in practice as opaque metal, transparent quartz, glass, and water. These facts are indirect, additional evidence that vision is the perception of electromagnetic waves.

Thus, the senses react to information presented in the form of waves. It is pretty easy to decompose a mountain landscape into a set of sinusoids, but Vysotsky perceives this as magnificence and sings: "only mountains can be better than mountains...". The eye perceives through a telescope the picture shown in the figure as a set of sinusoids. But Lermontov writes:

*It's solemn and extraordinary in the sky!
The Earth sleeps in a blue glow...*

7. Interaction of masses

It is necessary to consider one more component of the Universe - the interaction of masses in the Universe. (The attentive reader will notice that there is also the interaction of charges. But we can't do everything at once. Let's put this off until better times.)

It is now accepted that there are universal gravitational forces, discovered and mathematically described by the brilliant Newton. But he did not undertake to explain what it is. "I do not invent a prosthesis" - and leave me alone. And there are no claims against Newton: it is enough that he invented mechanics and differential calculus. However, modern physics accepts the existence of gravitational forces without justification and, at the same time, rejects the existence of other forces solely on the basis that no justification has been found for them [19]. However, if we are to understand what intelligent design consists of, we must also understand by what means and how this interaction is realized.

Celestial mechanics has a theory for calculating the trajectories of many bodies that interact with each other only through forces of mutual attraction. Poincaré proved that these trajectories are chaotic and unpredictable; the body can pass through the same point at different moments in time in different directions. Over an extended period, the trajectories acquire the appearance of a web. In the general case, these trajectories resemble truly random processes. This is the famous three-body problem. «*The discovery that a deterministic system can nevertheless have random features is a remarkable achievement,*» asserts mathematics [28]. Physics, which is looking for patterns that allow one to understand the structure of the world and navigate it, suddenly agreed, under the persuasion of mathematics, that in heaven everything is uncertain, unpredictable, and random!

Not all mathematical results have a physical interpretation. Wait, why should everything on Earth be deterministic? What right does physics have to assert the existence of physical laws? Here, on Earth, we are

convinced of the validity of these laws. And there, in the heavens, planets have been spinning strictly in the same orbit for centuries, the stars of the Galaxies rotate in a spiral, without getting tangled or jostling. These facts raise doubts about the validity of the problem statement.

In our search for an alternative solution, we will continue to utilize the mathematical material and tools - the same sinusoids and equations.

In [29, Chapter 18], it is proved that in a spherical body filled with mass particles, there are mass currents and gravimagnetic and gravioric strengths, and along with them, flows of **gravitational energy**. Everything is entirely analogous to what we previously considered for electrodynamics: 6 sinusoids represent the flow of energy. The only difference is that these sinusoids do not pulsate in time, but their amplitude can change in magnitude.

The flow of this energy rotates in the body of the sphere. But the main feature of this sphere is that this flow of energy can be transmitted to a neighboring sphere of a similar design. The gravitational interaction of masses is based on such exchanges. At the same time The Law of Universal Attraction needs to be clarified and can be clarified in such a way that the orbits of the planets are preserved, their stability is explained, the problem of many bodies is solved strictly (without chaos) and their rotation around their axis is taken into account (for example, the Mercury effect). Thus, in the heavens, there are no probabilities and chaos either [30]. We will not go into a detailed description of this interaction here.

The above allows us to assert that in celestial mechanics, it is necessary to utilize the concept of energy transfer through gravitational energy flows. Energy flows, as energy carriers, were introduced into science by Umov and Poynting. It is unacceptable to discuss the energy of interactions without also discussing how it is transferred, even if this method has not yet been discovered.

8. Decay and synthesis in the Universe

However, everyone knows that matter continuously radiates, which, according to science, foretells the heat death of the universe. I think the universe was created not to play, but forever. However, we then need to explain the process that opposes heat radiation. There is no point in hoping that (as some scientists claim) the vacuum will boil, howl, and particles will rush to the empty shore, because this contradicts the law of conservation of energy. It is also claimed that when two gamma quanta of high energy collide, a particle-antiparticle pair can be created. But where are the gamma quanta of high energy in heat radiation?

In [16] it is shown that there are strictly cylindrical waves. Such a wave not only moves, but also rotates around its axis. In [31] the case is considered when two such waves, like two cylinders, fly towards each other along their axes and, of course, rotate in opposite directions... And now, finally, they are connected by their opposite ends. After that, each cylinder will hold the opposite cylinder with its pressure. These pressures prevent the cylinders from touching, yet they are also the forces that bring the cylinders together. In this case, a standing wave will arise in each cylinder. Nothing prevents this pair of cylinders from existing indefinitely. In other words, this pair of cylinders forms a particle that has mass. The particle consists of two cylindrical parts rotating in different directions. It can be assumed that in this way, a neutrino is formed, which has a rest mass that agrees with experiments. In contrast, the existing theory states that neutrinos have zero rest mass.

Neutrinos are produced continuously in this manner. But in precisely the same way, larger cylindrical waves of thermal radiation are combined. This process of combination is opposed to the process of thermal decay.

Lately, unknown particles have been observed everywhere - augers or skyfish - see the picture. They are assumed to be an unknown species of insects. However, they are also photographed by parachutists at high altitudes, where insects have no purpose. It can be assumed that these are parts of electromagnetic waves, arising, breaking apart, and reassembling.

9. Conservation laws

In the first part it was said that particles (as mass) and waves (as energy flows) consist of groups of sinusoids, which include 3 sinusoids of electric strength and 3 sinusoids of magnetic strength. We will refer to such a group as the Ensemble of Six or, simply, **A6**. This is an inseparable group, similar to a vector - an ensemble of three. It is suitable for mechanics. Vector projections have in common that the vector modulus remains constant for any movement of the vector. And this thing pleased Maxwell's followers: many equations were written in 4 lines, and the solution was obtained in one line - the wave equation of an electromagnetic wave. This equation spread to other areas of physics and, one can say, quantum mechanics is built on its basis ... There is only one minor inconvenience - this solution does not satisfy the law of conservation of energy. But it satisfies this law on average, i.e., the law is

continuously violated, but in different directions, and on average, the energy has a constant value, like a normal temperature on average in a ward., But the doctors don't go home. The scientists didn't run away either, but made many things, and most importantly, the atomic bomb. I can say with confidence that all the results are very approximately correct, and many very useful solutions are simply a vector playing a cruel joke on electrodynamics. And the tensor... well, let's stop there: we have another topic.

But what unites the six sinusoids from which the External Mind built mass and energy? With any transformations, the total A6 energy remains constant [16]. A6 is indestructible and does not arise again. It is transmitted in the energy flow, in this same flow, it enters the particle and rotates in the internal flow. When the particle is destroyed, it enters the energy flow, etc./The total mass-energy of the Universe does not change. This is how the **law of conservation of energy** is "implemented". From conservation of energy follows conservation of energy flow, and the flow of momentum is proportional to it. Therefore, the **law of conservation of momentum** is also observed. From it, in turn, follows the **law of conservation of angular momentum**.

Let's look at the Ensemble of Six again. All the strengths in it are strengths that change sinusoidally in time. However, the total energy remains constant in time. It does not depend on frequency.

And here, a very delicate point arises. What will happen if the frequency is equal to zero?! The order in nature requires that everything happens the same way, as at a very low frequency, where oscillations occur in the ensemble, and it flies at the speed of light, as at any other frequency. Consequently, there must be a flow of energy flying at the speed of light, in which the sinusoids are frozen in time. But this contradicts common sense!

So what's going on?

Here is an experiment that answers this question. In [16, Chapter 7] it is shown that in a capacitor that is included in a DC circuit, there are flows of electromagnetic energy. And most importantly, it has been experimentally demonstrated that the flow of electromagnetic energy continues to circulate even after disconnection from the DC source. It remains even when the metal plates are removed, i.e., the energy of the capacitor is stored in the dielectric of the capacitor even in the absence of charges. The energy contained in the capacitor, which is considered to be electric potential energy, is electromagnetic energy stored in the capacitor in the form of a stationary flow. Additionally, an analytical solution to this problem was derived as one of the solutions to Maxwell's equations.

Here, we have received an answer to the question posed, which demonstrates that the Universe is a product of the activity of Reason, and not chance.

And how does science reason? The gravitational interaction between celestial bodies is transmitted by a constant force that attracts other bodies. The answer to the question has been found: there is no energy flow. However, we will show further that there is an energy flow and it moves at an enormous speed.

So, A6 saves energy, the value of which does not depend on the frequency of oscillations of sinusoids. The law of conservation of energy is not an order to save some constant. And its meaning is not the conservation of something limited in quantity - in the infinite Universe, there is enough of everything. The meaning of the law is to establish mathematical restrictions on any processes. Without restrictions, any process turns into chaos. A striking example is the equations of interaction of celestial bodies, the solutions of which are random (see Fig. 1 [32]), because they do not comply with conservation laws. These solutions were found by the works of the greatest mathematician of the 19th century. For example, as a rule, in the solutions it turns out that the barycenter of an autonomous group of celestial bodies has a constant speed, i.e., this group rushes through the expanses of the Universe. So what? There is somewhere to go, and there is no friction - it flies, preserving the momentum created by its forces. But it is impossible to obtain a patent for such an engine, because perpetual motion machines do not exist. The noble Academy does not concern itself with these issues: it is not a plebeian patent office. Poincaré did not think about this either; he believed that any mathematical solution has a physical interpretation. But mathematics is greater than physics.

Fig. 1.

Fig. 2.

The reader may say that I have chosen Fig. 1 to suit my reasoning, as it depicts a truly random trajectory. But aren't there deterministic solutions? Yes, there are, and celestial mechanics is proud of them – see, for example, Fig. 2. In my opinion, such a case looks much more random than the case in Fig. 2. A star or a planet flies in a straight line and suddenly turns 180 degrees. What could be more unnatural in mechanics?!

10. Maxwell's equations

In a discussion of mathematics, I do not want to distract the reader's attention with formulas, but, nevertheless, Maxwell's equations should be described for the sake of presentation - read more in [16]. As follows from the previous and will follow from the following, these equations are the most popular tool of the Supreme Intelligence for constructing the Universe. They can be written in any coordinate systems. In cylindrical coordinates r, φ, z they (along with the solutions of these equations) look the simplest. They contain vectors of electrical strength $\mathbf{E}_r, \mathbf{E}_\varphi, \mathbf{E}_z$, and magnetic strength $\mathbf{H}_r, \mathbf{H}_\varphi, \mathbf{H}_z$. These vectors are each on their own and are not combined into three-dimensional vectors. There are also electrical charges q and electric currents. Among them are conduction currents J and electric displacement currents $\frac{dE}{dt}$ are Maxwell's most controversial discovery. It is natural to call magnetic displacement currents $\frac{dH}{dt}$ the quantity .

In [16] it is proved that the conduction current is not a flow of electrons, but a **flow of autonomous charges** that arise in an electrically conducting wire when the energy flow moves along and inside the wire. The thermal motion of electrons appears as a result of the opposition of autonomous charges to the conduction current. Feynman called the idea that energy flows outside the wire "idiotic" [36], and the proposed concept explains why electrons move more slowly than an electric current. Additionally, this concept explains the effect of the Lorentz force, generated by the current in the wire, on the wire itself. Indeed, if the Lorentz force acted on the charges whose movement creates the current, this would mean that the charges move themselves! The proposed statement indicates that the current of additional charges moves the electrons of the wire and, together with them, the wire itself. For more details, see [16, Chapters 15 and 16].

In addition to equations, there are solutions to these equations. Here is the simplest of them - the solution for a cylindrical wave:

$$H_r = h_r(r) \text{co}, \quad (1)$$

$$H_\varphi = h_\varphi(r) \text{si}, \quad (2)$$

$$H_z = h_z(r) \text{si}, \quad (3)$$

$$E_r = e_r(r) \text{si}, \quad (4)$$

$$E_\varphi = e_\varphi(r) \text{co}, \quad (5)$$

$$E_z = e_z(r) \text{co}, \quad (6)$$

$$\text{co} = \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (7)$$

$$\text{si} = \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (8)$$

$$\chi = \omega / \sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}, \quad (9)$$

where $\alpha, \mu, \varepsilon, \omega$ are some constants, $h(r), e(r)$ are some coordinate functions r .

The Ensemble of Six cannot be discerned in the equations and solutions. The equation of electromagnetic energy density describes it:

$$W = \frac{1}{2} \left(\varepsilon (H_r^2 + H_\varphi^2 + H_z^2) + \mu (E_r^2 + E_\varphi^2 + E_z^2) \right). \quad (10)$$

Energy with this density is preserved in it during all the travels of the Ensemble of Six.

There are many different solutions, for example, for a wave, for a particle (cubic and spherical), for an electric wire, for a capacitor, for a three-phase machine, and for ball lightning, among others.

The equations themselves and their solutions can also be written in Cartesian or spherical coordinates. In the latter case, it follows directly from the solution of the equations that the energy flow from the sphere is

directed only to where there is an energy consumer. The sun shines and warms only the planets, and not everything around, as is assumed when calculating the strength of its radiation (when the strength of the Earth's radiation is considered average for space at a given radius).

11. Electric charge

Above, we said that there are WAP particles in which electromagnetic waves circulate. These particles have mass and participate in gravitational interactions. It is these masses that are included in Maxwell's gravitational equations [18].

The figure shows the WAP cube. Vectors of electric strengths emerge from the cube's faces, and therefore, this cube, having mass, is also an electric charge. It is these charges that enter into the usual electromagnetic equations of Maxwell.

In Maxwell's equations, electric charge is represented as the divergence of electric strengths - only three sinusoids out of an ensemble of six (see above). The same Maxwell equations also exist for gravity. But in them, the divergence of electrogravitational strengths is equivalent to gravitational mass, not electric charge.

Thus, Maxwell's equations are used at two levels. At the lower level, these equations are used to create particles, and at the upper level, these particles enter into the formulation of Maxwell's equations as charges for electrodynamics or masses for gravity.

An electron is an elementary particle that can "act as" an electric charge or a massive particle. An electron has a charge and a mass, obtained

by the same tension on the faces of this cube particle. This tension is interpreted in electrical engineering as the charge q of an electron, and in gravitation - as the mass m of an electron. Let's find their ratio in the SI system: m

$$q/m = 1,6 \cdot 10^{-19} / 9,1 \cdot 10^{-31} = 1,6 \cdot 10^{11}.$$

We cannot make the same comparisons for more complex, non-fundamental particles, since they are likely to be composed of multiple WAPs.

An electron, like a cubic WAP shown in the figure, interacts with its strengths with a neighboring mass as a mass, and with neighboring charges as a charge.

So, WAP is both a charge and a mass. In a specific body, a multitude of WAPs are summed up as a multitude of masses and mutually annihilate as a multitude of opposite charges. But a body can also be formed in which charges of a sure sign predominate. This body will be electrically charged.

Above, we discussed autonomous electric charges that are generated by the flow of electromagnetic energy. From what has been said, it follows that the Ensemble of Six, which was in the energy flow, directly passes from the energy flow into a particle-charge, which has mass. At the same time, the transformation of energy into mass transitions from a philosophical concept to a real process. The reverse transition is also possible.

12. Space and speed of energy flow

Everything exists in geometric space and time. Mathematics can depict any dimensional space and distort it in all dimensions. I think the Supreme Intelligence did not needlessly complicate the idea of constructing a knowable Universe. After all, a sine wave needs only three-dimensional space to exist, and even infinite time is not enough for humanity to fully know the Universe.

But what is space filled with? This question worries everyone. "Pseudo-scientists" believe that space is filled with ether, but they have not agreed on what it is. They argue: gas, liquid, crystalline, all-pervading and leaving room for something, etc. But "real scientists" have solved the problem radically: space is filled with vacuum, and it contains everything that Big Science may need - energy, particles, and maybe something else (life will show). However, there is no mention of ether. Representatives of quantum physics are particularly pleased with this decision.

What can we assume if we agree that the material for constructing the universe is sinusoids, and the most popular tool is Maxwell's equations?

From these equations, it follows that space must have electrical permeability ϵ and magnetic permeability μ . Maxwell guessed this and such space could be called ether or vacuum. But scientists of all kinds thought this was not enough.

But, in addition, the space must be such that energy exists in it in the form of a flow of energy moving at a speed

$$c = 1/\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}. \quad (1)$$

This also follows from Maxwell's equations. "Why do you always talk about these equations, as if there is nothing else?" the reader will exclaim. "Because it is these equations that determine the mode of existence of sinusoids in a form that can be interpreted physically."

So, $\mu, \epsilon, c = 1/\sqrt{\mu\epsilon}$ are the necessary properties of space.

Of course, space may have some other properties that do not violate conservation laws.

The values μ, ϵ, c of the quantities are determined experimentally for electrodynamics. But there is also gravity, which is also described by Maxwell's equations and in it are also determined

$$\mu_g, \epsilon_g, c_g = 1/\sqrt{\mu_g \epsilon_g}$$

- necessary properties of gravitational space. Therefore, we will call the above-defined μ, ϵ, c properties the properties of electrodynamic space

Thus, we can say that there are two spaces that differ in the values of permeability and the speed of propagation of the energy flow.

Recently, amazing experiments have been carried out - see the series of articles by Viktor Zaitsev [33]. Zaitsev has discovered and is **experimenting** with rays that differ in their radiation source and properties. Zaitsev has experimentally proven that there are solar rays that propagate at a speed much slower and much faster than the speed of light. Among the many amazing phenomena obtained in this fundamental discovery, we will be interested in the fact that there are 17 rays whose speeds are determined as follows. Let us consider the scale of numbers n these rays:

$$n=[-7, -6, \dots, -1, 0, 1, 2, \dots, 8, 9]. \quad (2)$$

Speed of propagation n -ray

$$v_n = \begin{cases} c \cdot F_1 \frac{1}{7-n}, & \text{if } n < 0, \\ c, & \text{if } n = 0, \\ c \cdot F_2 \frac{1}{9-n}, & \text{if } n > 0, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where F_1, F_2 are some constants. The most striking thing about this formula is that

$$v_9 = \infty. \quad (4)$$

Zaitsev explains this discovery by the existence of previously unknown particles - bosons, which are emitted not only by the photosphere of the Sun, but also by other - terrestrial sources of radiation. The existence of particles - carriers of radiation is based on the generally recognized fact of the existence of photons - carriers of electromagnetic radiation. However, above in section 4, the existence of the photon was refuted and therefore I will continue to bend my line: Zaitsev rays are waves of the same type as electromagnetic and gravitational waves. In Zaitsev waves, the speed of the wave - the flow of energy is also determined as

$$v = 1/\sqrt{\mu\varepsilon}. \quad (5)$$

If such velocities exist, it is necessary to recognize that they propagate in a space with other permeabilities, different from those considered above. We will call such a space μ, ε

$\mu\varepsilon$ -space,

and we will call the quantity $\mu\varepsilon$ the permeability of such a space. Until now, we could talk about two spaces - electrodynamic and gravitational. Zaitsev proved the existence of 17 spaces, among which there are two known ones. From this it follows [35], that:

1. several $\mu\varepsilon$ -spaces can exist in one geometric space;
2. any emitter emits a "fan" of 17 waves-flows of energy, spreading in 17 spaces; $\mu\varepsilon$
3. as permeability ; $(\mu \cdot \varepsilon)$ decreases, wave speed increases
4. substance X is in its own $\varepsilon_x \mu_x$ -space; the diversity of substances increases the multitude of $\mu\varepsilon$ -spaces.
5. the wave, having collided with the substance X, passes into its $\varepsilon_x \mu_x$ -space. Apparently, this happens for any wave
6. in $\mu\varepsilon$ -space with zero value $(\mu \cdot \varepsilon) = 0$ the speed is infinite. Such a space with zero permeability will be called **impenetrable space**. The paradoxical thing is that it is precisely this space that the wave beam penetrates with infinite speed. And it was discovered in

Zaitsev's experiments with the error that is explained by the unattainability of infinity. $(\mu \cdot \varepsilon) = 0$

13. Entangled particles

The particle-and-wave construction proposed above might shake the self-critical quantum physicist's confidence in his own rightness. But entangled particles, whose existence has been experimentally proven, will restore his confidence. Where is the electrostatics of the macrocosm?

Meanwhile, something similar can be observed in the macro world: *“Stormglasses behave absolutely identically everywhere – even in very distant countries. As long as the solution is from the same vessel.”* [16, chapter 28]. There, a mathematical model of such particles is considered, which instantly communicates some information to each other without spending energy on receiving and transmitting this information. It has been proven that particles capable of emitting and receiving radiation, as well as having a common frequency of reception and transmission, are entangled, i.e., they can exchange instantaneous messages, regardless of the distance between them, without expending energy.

From Maxwell's equations, it follows that there is a cylindrical wave in which in one physical cylinder, the energy flows are directed towards each other and rotate in opposite directions, without interacting with each other. Fig. 1 shows the end points A and B of the spirals. Let us place some structures called "emitter-receiver" - ER - at these points. ER radiates an electromagnetic wave and receives an electromagnetic wave emitted by the opposite ER. The radiated and received waves carry the same energy flow. Therefore, such a structure does not spend energy on transmitting the energy flow. Energy is spent by ER on analyzing the received flow and creating an opposite flow with the same magnitude of the flow. The analysis may involve determining the magnitude of the flow. The value of the received flow may be information for the receiver, based on which it can change the value of the sent flow or change this value in accordance with its internal state (or, perhaps, in accordance with the content of information received over a period of time). In this way, the coordinated behavior of a pair of ERs can be organized.

We have received, so to speak, an entangled pair of ER. It is entangled with the help of a cylindrical wave, which can be arbitrarily long and does not lose energy along the way. A pair of entangled ER does not spend energy to transmit and receive information. Such a cylindrical wave in an impenetrable $\mu\varepsilon$ -space with zero value $(\mu \cdot \varepsilon) = 0$ exchange of information will occur without time delay.

Fig. 1.

14. Dark Matter

Dark matter has been experimentally detected; it occupies most of the universe's volume, but its structure remains undetermined. In Section 4 and in [13] it is shown that one of the solutions of Maxwell's equations is a spherical standing wave, on the surface of which all strengths are zero and there is no radial energy flow. Its volume is unlimited. An energy flow circulates in its volume, and therefore it has mass, but cannot be detected, since it does not emit waves. This property makes such a sphere dark matter

15. On the interaction of consciousness and matter

The structure of the material world was discussed above. The behavior of its fragments may be meaningless. However, there is meaningful behavior of matter, controlled by consciousness. Humans commit conscious acts and possess free will. If we agree that the Supreme Intelligence created the Universe, then we must admit that free will exists. The Supreme Intelligence would not create a Universe whose behavior is predetermined. This is simply a senseless undertaking. It is the same as making a car and constantly dragging it by a string. In addition, we must also agree that the Supreme Intelligence interferes in worldly affairs.

But not only do humans possess consciousness. The concept of panpsychism is well known, where the presence of some share of consciousness is recognized for any form of matter and at all scales, from celestial bodies and their clusters to elementary particles. But how does

consciousness interact with matter? Experience shows that by an effort of will, we cannot (as a rule) create a force effect. The general recognition of panpsychism is held back by the fact that there is no visible method or **mediator** for transmitting the impact of consciousness on matter. This issue is examined in detail in [37], where this mediator is referred to as the **minimal agency of the issue**. To solve the issue, mathematics is used, “stunning” in its volume, complexity, and diversity. But the answer has not yet been found.

Such an intermediary should not create a force or change the coordinates of the material body and, in general, in any way transfer energy to this body. Consequently, the body should have some parameter that is not observable and not measurable, but accessible to influence from the side of consciousness. The value of this parameter should significantly affect the characteristics of the body and its movement. An intermediary with such properties should be inaccessible to measurement and change at the level of modern knowledge, but should be included in the list of calculated parameters. Perhaps someday we will learn to perceive the change in this parameter or even alter its value through physical influence. Perhaps this will happen only after we understand what consciousness is.

If such a mediator exists, then an explanation for the most controversial postulate of quantum mechanics appears – the assertion that the observer changes the properties of a wave-particle. This assertion assumes that the observed object changes its properties during measurement or even radically transforms from a wave to a particle and back depending on the experimental conditions. Everything is simpler: a **wave-AND-particle** object can change its characteristics and even behave as either a wave or a particle due to this. Such properties of a wave-AND-particle are considered in [17].

Here the observer's expectations through his consciousness and the object's parameter affect the object. The hypnotist affects the patient in the same way, and the yogi affects his own body.

But how does consciousness affect such a parameter? The answer to this question will probably be found together with the understanding of consciousness. However, the search for this parameter can be declared even today.

Let's consider an example. In an electric circuit there are electric currents and voltages, electric and magnetic intensities. In electrical engineering, all these quantities are described by functions of the form

$$F(\varphi, t) = A \cdot \sin(\varphi_0 + \varphi + \omega t), \quad (1)$$

where A is the amplitude, ω is the angular frequency, t is the time, φ is the phase, φ_0 is the initial phase. The parameters φ, ω, t are common to all functions.

When calculating the circuit, the amplitudes of all functions are determined. If electrical engineering problems are solved as a system of Maxwell's equations [16], then all functions in the cylindrical coordinate system r, φ, z must be written in the form

$$S = A(r) \cdot \sin(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t) \quad (2)$$

or

$$C = A(r) \cdot \cos(\alpha\varphi + \chi z + \omega t), \quad (3)$$

where $A(r)$ is the amplitude depending on r , χ is the value reciprocal to the wavelength, α is some parameter common to all functions. When calculating the circuit, the functions $A(r)$ are determined, which are different for all functions (2,3), and the parameter α , common to all functions. Formally, it depends on the power consumed by this circuit. But it exists before the circuit is connected to the energy source. It exists objectively. **It was created by nature.** The energy generator has produced such power that can be spent by this circuit. In this sense, the parameter α is the same value as ohmic resistance - it determines the request for the generator for the amount of power. For example, the power determined by the resistance of the bulb and the value of the parameter α in the electric circuit with the bulb will flow from the socket to the bulb. If two circuits are identical, then the parameters α in them are equal. But there is probably a psychic who will make one of the bulbs burn brighter.

Thus, there is a parameter in the electric circuit that facilitates communication with consciousness, which we have been seeking. We stated above that all matter consists of A6 ensembles and, ultimately, of sinusoids of the form (2, 3). Therefore, **all matter is ready to obey consciousness.** But the question of what consciousness is remains unanswered.

16. Conclusions

1. **All equations of physics are a consequence of the principle of the extremum of complete action**, which are conditions of the extremum of some functional. This functional is the same for ALL areas of physics and ALWAYS has a SINGLE extremum, which creates an inviolable order in the universe. Such uniformity cannot be a consequence of chance. The spontaneous, random appearance of solutions to the most complex mathematical problems, interpreting the real physical world,

without the intervention of the Author who solved these problems, is impossible.

2. Mass (substance) is a certain set of standing waves.

3. Energy exists in the form of energy flows - this is a certain set of traveling waves.

4. All interactions in the Universe represent an exchange of energy flows equivalent to wave flows.

5. Organic life was created **after some complex mathematical problem was solved.**

6. The brain, with its sense organs, perceives the world as a set of waves

7. **A wave in mass and energy is a set of sinusoids** that are mathematical abstractions (i.e., it is not a change in anything). Mass and energy are made from a mathematical variable. This variable does not need to be made. It is publicly available.

8. **Mass and energy are made from sinusoids using Maxwell's equations as the tool to create them.** The use of mathematical abstractions as objects of random enumeration or construction is impossible in any real process.

9. **In the solutions of Maxwell's equations,** there is a specific parameter that is not observable and not measurable. The value of this parameter has a significant impact on the body's characteristics and movement. The value of this parameter is determined during the solution of the equations. **The influence of consciousness can change such a parameter.**

We can say that everything is made of mathematics and occurs in accordance with mathematical equations that have a universal character. And this statement applies both to inanimate matter and organic life, as it is described mathematically.

Of course, there is a Higher Mind that has accomplished all this.

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